

UNIVERSITY OF
TORONTO

Highly Flexible and Self-Healable Electronic Skin

Sung Hwa Hong, Harvey HaoTian Shi, Guorui Wang, Tobin Filleter, Hani E. Naquib

Department of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering
Department of Materials Science and Engineering
University of Toronto, Ontario, Canada

Toronto Smart Materials & Structures
University of Toronto

The Needs for Next Generation of Flexible Electronics

- ❖ **Electronics degrade over time** due to fatigue, environmental conditions, or damages incurred during operation leading to eventual failure of the material.

© azonano.com

Flexible circuit

© technologyreview.com

Electronic tattoo

Sci. Adv., 2019, 5, eaay0418

Wearable sensor

© Samsung

Portable Device

Limitation

- **Shortens** lifetime of device
- **Changes/weakens** original integrity
- Causes device **malfunctioning**

Functionalities of Flexible Electronics

Motivation and Objectives

Motivation

- ❖ Facile methodology for flexible electronics with high-performing device performance
- ❖ Substrate material for **long-term utilization** of devices
 - ❖ Material exhibiting the **self-healing properties with high toughness**

Objectives

- ❖ Fabricate supercapacitor through **facile methodology**
- ❖ Design and synthesize **self-healing polymer** for flexible electronics
- ❖ Achieve **high toughness material** that exhibits self-healing behavior

Challenges

Self-Healing

Toughness

Weak interaction

➤ Chain flexibility / mobility

Strong interaction

➤ Low chain flexibility / mobility

Reported strategies to enhance toughness for smart skin:

- 1) Addition of filler
- 2) Molecular modification of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS)
- 3) Molecular modification of polyurethane (PU)

In Situ Fabrication of Fibrous Gel-Elastomer for Exceptionally Tough Material

SP

Key Properties

- Low Young's modulus (< 5MPa)
- Rate/efficiency of healing
- Stretchability

Limitation

- Low toughness

PU

Key Properties

- High toughness
- Stretchability

Limitation

- High Young's Modulus
- Limited self-healability

Blend!

SP = self-healing polymer
PU = polyurethane

Fabrication of SPB Gel-Elastomer

SP/PU weight ratio = 1/1
 Fe(III) / COOH molar ratio = 0.5 - 5

Smart Skin

Fabrication of SPB Gelastomer

Mechanical Properties of SPBs

Type of polymer/ crosslinker	Young's modulus (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)	Toughness (MJ/m ³)
SPB1-Fe0.5	2.38 ± 0.71	456 ± 39	7.8 ± 1.0
SPB1-Fe1	3.40 ± 0.62	809 ± 60	31.3 ± 3.5
SPB1-Fe3	3.11 ± 0.40	552 ± 126	15.2 ± 2.9
SPB1-Fe5	2.19 ± 0.24	447 ± 88	7.9 ± 3.0
SPB3-Fe1	1.82 ± 0.13	335 ± 86	3.7 ± 1.7
PU	8.65 ± 0.85	1020 ± 159	100.9 ± 20.0

- **Young's modulus was significantly reduced.**
- **Relatively high toughness was achieved.**
- **High fracture strain** due to transient bonding that dissipates the stretching energy through association-dissociation

Mechanical Properties of SPB

- **Young's modulus was significantly reduced.**
- **Toughness was enhanced.**
- **High fracture strain** due to transient bonding that dissipates the stretching energy through association-dissociation

Self-Healing Capability of SPB

Macro-indentation

Nanoindentation

Self-Healing Test at Macroscale

SPB1-Fe1

PU

- Macro-indentation experiment is representative of damages from everyday life.
- Optical microscopic images show that the self-healing polymer blend heals at room temperature without any energy input.

Self-Healing Test at Microscale

Tactile Sensing Capability of SPB

SPB as an Energy Storage Device

Symmetrical cell using
1 M H₂SO₄ and voltage up to 1.2 V

Conclusion

- **Gel and elastomer polymer blend** has not been studied for highly tough and self-healing material.
- Homogenous and freestanding material was obtained from **electrospinning in-situ**.
- Achieved a **high toughness** below 5 MPa of Young's Modulus.
- Efficient healing at room temperature without any external aid.
- Demonstrated the capability for smart skin as an energy storage device and tactile sensors.

Thank You for Your Attention!